

Mini Guide to eSports Journalism

Practices, challenges, and digital transformations

João Pedro Ferreira
Marcos Américo
Ruth S. Contreras Espinosa

About This mini guide

This guide examines the constitution of specialized journalism in eSports, understanding it as a manifestation of the contemporary transformations of journalism in the digital environment. Based on a narrative bibliographic and documentary review, as well as a qualitative content analysis in multiple case studies, the study identifies historical milestones, theoretical foundations, and emerging practices that shape this field. The corpus includes academic literature indexed in Scopus and Web of Science and journalistic records of pioneering events since the 1980s, emphasizing the transition from traditional coverage models to interactive ecosystems mediated by platforms such as Twitch and YouTube. This project also analyzes journalistic channels on live streaming platforms, arguing that eSports journalism is not merely a thematic niche but a laboratory for the epistemological, narrative, and professional changes that characterize contemporary journalism. It concludes that specialization in eSports exemplifies the reconfiguration of routines, news values, and legitimation strategies in the context of convergence and digital participation, contributing to a broader understanding of innovation and mediation processes in journalistic practice.

KEYWORDS: Specialized journalism; eSports; Digital convergence; Participatory culture; Journalistic innovation.

This project was developed in November 2025 within the scope of BEPE/FAPESP (Research Internship Scholarship Abroad) by João Pedro Amaral Gonçalves Ferreira (BEPE fellow), under the guidance of Marcos Américo (project advisor, UNESP) and the supervision of Ruth S. Contreras Espinosa (supervisor at the University of Barcelona), in partnership between UNESP and the University of Barcelona. This guide is intended to serve as a supporting resource for students and educators interested in understanding and analyzing journalistic practices related to eSports, both within the academic sphere and in the professional media market. It compiles studies and analyses conducted by the researchers, in articles and other scholarly works, with the purpose of providing a comprehensive overview of specialized journalism in electronic sports.

Authors:

João Pedro Amaral Gonçalves Ferreira - Universidade Estadual Paulista, Bauru, São Paulo Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0007-4708-6728

Marcos Américo - Universidade Estadual Paulista, Bauru, São Paulo Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-7920-4513

Ruth S. Contreras Espinosa - University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain
ORCID: 0009-0007-4708-6728

Any comments relating to the material contained in this document may be sent to jpa.ferreira@unesp.br

Introduction

Esports Market Size 2024 to 2034 (USD Billion)

Source: <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/esports-market>

Electronic sports, or eSports, are now a rapidly expanding global phenomenon, attracting millions of followers around the world and establishing themselves as one of the fastest-growing competitive markets (Zagala & Strzelecki, 2019; Stoeber, 2021). According to López-Cabarcos et al. (2024), eSports have significant economic and social potential; the consulting firm Precedence Research estimates that the global gaming market will reach \$303.47 billion by this year, with eSports accounting for approximately 3% of that amount. This study highlights that while games have a growth rate of 10.24% in the period presented, eSports have a growth rate of 21.98%.

eSports have become a multifaceted phenomenon, spanning domains such as gaming, entertainment, media, culture, arts, education, business, diversity, and inclusion, taking on both local and global characteristics (Scholz & Nothelfer, 2022; Kutlu, 2025).

The popularization of eSports contributes to the theoretical debate in the field of contemporary journalism, especially segmented coverage. According to Taylor (2012), "eSports still need the specialized press to continue expanding and sustaining this [media] space." Scholz's (2020) discussion of the constitution of eSports as a sociocultural phenomenon that has evolved beyond the constraints of traditional sports, media, entertainment, and culture expands the debate to a segmented professionalization of journalism in this area.

Early media milestones in eSports

1980

The Space Invaders Championship (1980) represents the first large-scale tournament promoted by a video game company. The competition brought together thousands of participants in regional stages and attracted attention from the print and television media.

The creation of Twin Galaxies (1981) by Walter Day institutionalized the collection and dissemination of gaming records and statistics. The link with the Guinness Book of World Records reinforced the public legitimacy of the results, providing verifiable material for journalists.

1981

The formation of the U.S. National Video Game Team in 1983 marked the beginning of the professionalization of competitive gaming, positioning players as national representatives and attracting greater media coverage.

1983

In the 1990s, the spread of the internet transformed face-to-face tournaments into online championships, creating conditions for the media globalization of the phenomenon. Networked leagues and LAN party events offered new spaces for serious and professional competitions, expanding the reach and complexity of coverage.

1990s

Technological advances have accelerated the shift from offline to online, consolidating eSports as one of the most profound evolutionary movements in the media industry of the 21st century. eSports are now being studied as a global and hybrid phenomenon, spanning domains such as media, culture, education, and entertainment.

2000s-now

Media coverage and journalistic specialization

The association of eSports with traditional sports remains a central point of debate, as it involves both the conceptual definition of sport and the media legitimacy of digital competitions. Américo (2014) argues that video games can be considered sports as the very concept of sport evolves historically. In contrast, Wagner (2006) maintains that eSports constitute a unique field of study, not limited by the traditional definition of sport, but characterized by its own cultural and scientific values. Jenny et al. (2017), Hallmann and Giel (2018), and Jonasson and Thiborg (2010) reinforce this debate by exploring the extent to which eSports can be classified as a sport or as a competitive recreational activity. This conceptual diversity shows that the academic and media relevance of eSports does not depend exclusively on classifying them as a sport, but on analyzing them as an autonomous phenomenon.

From a theoretical point of view, Juski (2020) and Seijas Candelas (2003) understand specialized journalism as a response to the social need for in-depth thematic coverage, providing the public with detailed knowledge tailored to their interests. Justino (2022) reinforces that, in the case of eSports, specialization seeks to inform in an attractive and consistent manner, balancing entertainment and professionalism.

Media coverage of eSports reveals a movement toward specialization that articulates three main dimensions: (a) conceptual, affirming eSports as a unique and culturally relevant phenomenon (Wagner, 2006; Scholz, 2020; Jenny et al., 2017; Hallmann & Giel, 2018; Jonasson & Thiborg, 2010); (b) linguistic and narrative, by developing its own styles of narration and vocabulary (Torres-Toukoumidis et al., 2022; Wilbert, 2018); and (c) editorial, by consolidating specific spaces on both interactive digital platforms and traditional media (Perreault & Perreault, 2021; Rodríguez, 2019; Freitas, Contreras-Espinosa & Correia, 2020, 2021). These elements demonstrate that specialization is not just a thematic adaptation, but a redefinition of journalistic practices in the face of an emerging and interactive field.

Definition of eSports journalism

Journalistic practice dedicated to covering competitive video game ecosystems, combining in-depth thematic analysis, specific formats and languages, and constant interaction with digital communities, with the aim of informing, interpreting, and culturally legitimizing eSports as a unique sociocultural phenomenon.

Thematic Focus

Coverage of tournaments, players, organizations, communities, and competitive practices.

Language and format

Use of hybrid narratives (technical and emotional), real-time narration, interactivity, and adaptation to the digital ecosystem.

Social function

Mediation between gamer culture and the general public, acting as a cultural legitimizer and vehicle for qualified interpretation.

Esports journalism differs from both traditional sports journalism and gaming journalism. Unlike the classic sports model, esports coverage is structured around participatory digital ecosystems and adapts its genres to synchronous and co-productive routines. On the other hand, unlike gaming journalism, which focuses on previews and reviews (Tibúrcio, 2013; Thomas, 2013), specialized coverage focuses on competition, tournaments and community mediation (Wilbert, 2018; Hamari & Sjöblom, 2017; Hilvert-Bruce et al., 2018).

Torres-Toukoumidis et al. (2022) highlight that eSports coverage requires specific routines: real-time narration, technical vocabulary, complex audiovisual production, and integration with digital platforms. Wilbert (2018) observes that this vocabulary is highly volatile, requiring constant updating to keep up with expressions created in live streams, forums, and social networks. This shows that eSports coverage requires adaptation to a hybrid language that combines technicality with emotion and informality in order to engage with young audiences and digital communities.

Conclusion & Reflection Questions

The reflections show that the establishment of journalism specializing in eSports is not limited to a new thematic segment, but expresses a structural transformation of the journalistic field itself in the face of mediatization and digital convergence.

eSports journalism presents itself as a privileged laboratory for observing contemporary changes in journalism, in terms of professionalization, narrative and ethics, while reaffirming the need to rethink the criteria for specialization in the context of digital culture. It can be concluded that studying eSports journalism means understanding the ways in which journalism reinvents itself, negotiates boundaries, and reaffirms its social relevance in increasingly interactive and fragmented information environments.

It was found that the use of live streaming platforms such as Twitch and YouTube has decisively transformed the languages, formats, and practices of eSports journalism. The journalistic activity of electronic sports has come to incorporate interactive practices, hybrid languages, and forms of engagement that reconfigure the role of the journalist as a cultural mediator. This specialization highlights an epistemological shift: journalism no longer acts solely as an observer but has become part of participatory ecosystems, where audiences, producers, and brands share practices of mediation and legitimacy.

It was also possible to conclude that journalistic specialization in eSports has significant cultural and social value. It legitimizes eSports as a unique sociocultural phenomenon (Heikkilä et.al, 2018; Scholz & Nothelfer, 2022), broadens social participation through active and co-producing communities (Jenkins et al., 2015), and reinforces the understanding of video games as interactive ecosystems that span sport, media, and culture (Perreault & Vos, 2018).

References

Abreu Freitas, B. D., Contreras-Espinosa, R. S., & Correia, P. Á. P. (2021). Esports sponsorships: The double-edged sword effect of having a very vocal audience. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Videogame Sciences and Arts* (pp. 1–14).

Abreu Freitas, B. D., Contreras-Espinosa, R. S., & Pereira Correia, P. Á. (2020). Identifying the pros, cons and tactics of eSports sponsorships: An integrative literature review. *Comunicação Pública: Revista Multidisciplinar de Comunicação*, 15(28). <https://doi.org/10.4000/cp.7243>

Américo, M. (2014). O jornalismo esportivo transmídia no ecossistema dos esportes eletrônicos (E-Sports). *Estudos em Jornalismo e Mídia*, 11(2), 316.

Hallmann, K., & Giel, T. (2018). eSports – Competitive sports or recreational activity? *Sport Management Review*, 21(1), 14–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smr.2017.07.011>

Heikkilä, R., Lauronen, T., & Purhonen, S. (2018). The crisis of cultural journalism revisited: The space and place of culture in quality European newspapers from 1960 to 2010. *European Journal of Cultural Studies*, 21(6), 669–686. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1367549416682970>

Hilvert-Bruce, Z., Neill, J. T., Sjöblom, M., & Hamari, J. (2018). Social motivations of live-streaming viewer engagement on Twitch. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 84, 58–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.02.013>

Jenkins, H., Ito, M., & boyd, d. (2015). *Participatory culture in a networked era: A conversation on youth, learning, commerce, and politics*. Cambridge, UK: Polity Press.

Jenny, S. E., Manning, R. D., Keiper, M. C., & Olrich, T. W. (2017). Virtual(ly) athletes: Where eSports fit within the definition of sport. *Quest*, 69(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00336297.2016.1144517>

Jonasson, K., & Thiborg, J. (2010). Electronic sport and its impact on future sport. *Sport in Society*, 13(2), 287–299. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17430430903522996>

Juski, J. R., Hoff, R. S., & Forechi, M. (2020). *Jornalismo especializado* [eBook]. Porto Alegre: SAGAH. <https://integrada.minhabiblioteca.com.br/#/books/9786556900698>

Kutlu, D. (2025). A bibliometric analysis using Vosviewer of publications on esports. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Academic Tourism*, 10(2), 149–163. <https://doi.org/10.31822/jomat.2025-10-2-149>

López-Cabarcos, M. Á., Caby, J., Sixto Lugilde, S. A., & Piñeiro-Chousa, J. (2024). An approach to innovative eSports from a business perspective. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 9(4), 100555. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2024.100555>

Perreault, G., & T. (2020). Metajournalistic on the of gaming *New Media & Culture*, 22(1), 159–176.

Precedence Research. (2024). eSports market. Retrieved from <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/esports-market#:~:text=The%20global%20eSports%20market%20size%20was%20calculated%20at%20USD%206.61,forecast%20period%202025%20to%202034>

Precedence Research. (2024). Video game market. Retrieved from <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/video-game-marke>

Rodríguez, A. P. (2019). E-sports y medios de comunicación. *Creatividad y Sociedad*.

Scholz, T. M. (2020). Deciphering the world of eSports. *International Journal on Media Management*, 22(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14241277.2020.1757808>

Scholz, T. M., & Nothelfer, N. (2022). Research for CULT Committee: Esports—background analysis. *European Parliament*. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/IPOL_STU\(2022\)6996_35](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/IPOL_STU(2022)6996_35)

Seijas Candelas, L. (2003). *Estructura y fundamentos del periodismo especializado* [eBook]. España: Universitas.

Stoever, J. K. (2021). Title IX, esports, and #EToo. *George Washington Law Review*, 89, 857–905. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3894496>

Taylor, T. L. (2012). *Raising the stakes: E-sports and the professionalization of computer gaming*. MIT Press.

Thomas, A. P. dos S. (2017). *Jornalismo de jogos: Da origem à recepção* (Monografia de graduação). Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Escola de Comunicação, Centro de Filosofia e Ciências Humanas.

Tibúrcio, M. R. (2013). *O jornalismo de games na internet brasileira* (Trabalho de Conclusão de Curso, Comunicação Social – Jornalismo). Escola de Comunicação, Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro. <https://hdl.handle.net/11422/3720>

Torres-Toukoudidis, A., Marín-Gutiérrez, I., & Caldeiro Pedreira, M. C. (2022). Communication experts' perspective on Esports. In *Esports and the media* (pp. 104–112). London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003273691-10>

Wagner, M. G. (2006). On the scientific relevance of eSports. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Internet Computing*.

Wilbert, C. S. A. (2018). *Jornalismo e e-sports: Uma análise da cobertura jornalística aplicada a esportes eletrônicos no Brasil* (Monografia de graduação). Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Faculdade de Biblioteconomia e Comunicação, Departamento de Comunicação.

Zagała, K., & Strzelecki, A. (2019). eSports evolution in football game series. *Physical Culture and Sport. Studies and Research*, 83(1), 50–62. <https://doi.org/10.2478/pcssr-2019-0020>